

Interactions of Mono-, Di- and Trialkylammonium Ions in Solution from Partial Molal Volume Study*

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Partial molal volume data of mono-, di-, and trialkylammonium ($R_xNH_{4-x}^+$) ions have been used to examine their hydrophobic behaviours in aqueous solution. The semiempirical equation, proposed earlier for studying hydrophobic interactions of tetraalkylammonium (R_4N^+) ions, appears to hold well also for $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$ ions in solution.

RECENTLY¹, it has been shown that the volume change in the solute-solvent systems due to the hydrophobic interactions of tetraalkylammonium ions (R_4N^+) in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions can be expressed by a simple semiempirical equation involving the partial molal volume of R_4N^+ ions at infinite dilution (\bar{V}'_{ion}) and the number of the carbon atoms (n_c) present in such ions.

$$\bar{V}'_{ion} - \bar{V}'_{cryst} = An_c + B/n_c \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where A and B are constants. An_c and B/n_c represent the volume changes due to the structural rearrangements among the solvent water molecules, \bar{V}'_{H_2O} , and due to the partial hiding of the hydrocarbon groups in the cage formation \bar{V}'_{caging} , respectively². Mono-, di- and trialkylammonium ions are also hydrophobic because like tetraalkylammonium ions they also contain non-polar hydrocarbon groups which are believed to be responsible for the hydrophobicity of the ions. It would be therefore reasonable to assume that these ions should also follow the same pattern of ion-solvent interactions. In this context, it would be interesting to see whether the hydrophobic behaviours of the partially substituted ammonium ions ($R_xNH_{4-x}^+$) in water can be described by eqn. (1). In the present paper the available partial molal volume data of mono-, di- and trialkylammonium salts³⁻⁵ in water were used for examining the applicability of eqn. (1) and also for calculating the respective values of \bar{V}'_{H_2O} ($=An_c$) and \bar{V}'_{caging} ($=B/n_c$) for these ions in solution.

Results

Equation (1) contains \bar{V}'_{cryst} term which may be obtained by assuming the ions to be hard spheres ($3\pi r^3 N/4 = 2.523r^3$) if the crystal radius r is known. Radius r of tetraalkylammonium ions (R_4N^+), i.e., when $x=4$ in $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$ ions, calculated by the method recommended by Robinson and Stokes⁶, can form a smooth curve when plotted against the corresponding number of carbon atoms (n_c) in the

ions (Fig. 1). In the present work it would be assumed that the radius for $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$ ions when the value of x is other than 4, also falls in the same

Fig. 1. Plot of crystal radius (r , Å) of R_xN^+ ions vs their respective number of the carbon atoms (n_c).

curve. The radii of various $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$ ions have been interpolated from Fig. 1, and are listed in column 2 of Table 1, while column 3 contains the values of \bar{V}'_{cryst} ($=2.523r^3$) for these ions.

Partial molal volume of ions of the type $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$, such as, RNH_3^+ , $R_2NH_2^+$ and R_3NH^+ have been calculated from the literature values of those of the corresponding halides³⁻⁵, and the values of the halide ions⁴. These results are listed in columns 4 and 6 of Table 1 while columns 5 and 7 contain the values of the difference $\bar{V}'_{ion} - \bar{V}'_{cryst}$ at 25° and 55°, respectively. Equation (1) may be rearranged to give eqns. (2) and (3) that are suitable

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TABLE 1—VALUES OF \bar{V}°_{ion} , \bar{V}°_{cryst} , AND $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ OF VARIOUS $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$ IONS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION (IN cm^3/mol).

ions	r	\bar{V}°_{cryst}	25°		55°	
			\bar{V}°_{ion}	$\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$	\bar{V}°_{ion}	$\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$
MeNH ₃ ⁺	3.00	68.0	30.7	-37.3	30.4	-37.6
EtNH ₃ ⁺	3.15	78.8	47.5	-31.3	48.0	-30.8
PrNH ₃ ⁺	3.32	92.2	64.0	-28.2	64.5	-27.7
BuNH ₃ ⁺	3.47	105.3	80.1	-25.2		
PenNH ₃ ⁺	3.60	117.6	96.0	-21.6		
HexNH ₃ ⁺	3.73	130.8	112.0	-18.8		
HepNH ₃ ⁺	3.88	147.2	127.7	-19.5	131.4	-15.8
OctNH ₃ ⁺	4.00	161.3	143.7	-17.6	147.6	-13.7
Me ₂ NH ₂ ⁺	3.15	78.8	49.3	-29.5		
Et ₂ NH ₂ ⁺	3.47	105.3	83.6	-21.7		
Pr ₂ NH ₂ ⁺	3.73	130.3	115.3	-15.5		
Me ₃ NH ₂ ⁺	3.32	92.2	68.0	-24.2		
Et ₃ NH ₂ ⁺	3.73	130.8	115.4	-15.4		
Pr ₃ NH ₂ ⁺	4.14	178.8	163.6	-15.2		

for testing graphically the predicted dependence of $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ and hence of \bar{V}°_{ion} on the number of carbon atoms present in the ion.

$$(\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst})n_c = An_c^2 + B \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$(\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst})/n_c = A + B/n_c^2 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Plots of eqns. (2) and (3) for various $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$ ions are shown in Figs. 2-4. Plot of eqn. (2) makes the data corresponding to ions having smaller value of n_c compressed while the plot of eqn. (3) shows the reverse. Thus both plots would clearly show the best overall confirmation of the applicability of eqn. (1) for all of the ions. From the slopes and intercepts of the lines in the two kinds of plots the constant A and B for different ions have been determined and presented in Table 2. With the help of the values of A and B, thus obtained, $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$ ($=An_c$) and of \bar{V}°_{caging} ($=B/n_c$) for various $R_xNH_{4-x}^+$ ions have been calculated and listed in Table 3.

Fig. 2. Plots of $(\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst})/n_c$ vs n_c^2 for RNH_3^+ ions in solution, at two different temperatures, (O at 25° and Δ at 55°).

Fig. 3. Plots of $(\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst})/n_c$ vs $1/n_c^2$ for RNH_3^+ ions in solution, at two different temperatures, (O at 25° and Δ at 55°).

Fig. 4. Plots of $(\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst})/n_c$ vs n_c^2 , and $(\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst})/n_c$ vs $1/n_c^2$ for $R_2NH_2^+$ and $R_3NH_2^+$ ions in solution, at 25°, (O for $R_2NH_2^+$ and Δ for $R_3NH_2^+$ ions).

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CONSTANTS A AND B (in cm³/mol) OF Eq. (1) FOR VARIOUS R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ IONS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

Ions	25°C		55°C	
	A	B	A	B
RNH ₃ ⁺	-1.1	-80	-0.6	-80
R ₂ NH ₂ ⁺	-0.8	-60		
R ₃ NH ⁺	-0.8	-60		
R ₄ N ⁺ ^a	-2.0	-5	-1.9 ^b	-40 ^b

^a reference 1
^b at 50°C.

 TABLE 3—VALUES OF $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$ (=An_c) AND \bar{V}°_{caging} (=B/n_c) FOR VARIOUS R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ IONS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION, (in cm³/mol)

Ions	25°C		55°C	
	$\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$	\bar{V}°_{caging}	$\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$	\bar{V}°_{caging}
MeNH ₃ ⁺	-1.1	-80.0	-0.6	-80.0
EtNH ₂ ⁺	-2.2	-40.0	-1.2	-40.0
PrNH ₂ ⁺	-3.3	-26.7	-1.8	-26.7
BuNH ₂ ⁺	-4.4	-20.0	-2.4	-20.0
PenNH ₂ ⁺	-5.5	-16.0	-3.0	-16.0
HexNH ₂ ⁺	-6.6	-13.3	-3.6	-13.3
HepNH ₂ ⁺	-7.7	-11.4	-4.2	-11.4
OctNH ₂ ⁺	-8.8	-10.0	-4.8	-10.0
Me ₂ NH ₂ ⁺	-1.6	-30.0		
Et ₂ NH ₂ ⁺	-3.2	-15.0		
Pr ₂ NH ₂ ⁺	-4.8	-10.0		
Me ₃ NH ⁺	-2.4	-20.0		
Et ₃ NH ⁺	-4.8	-10.0		
Pr ₃ NH ⁺	-7.2	-6.7		

Discussion

It is evident from Table 1 (columns 5 and 7) that for all R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ ions the value of $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ is negative. This means that these ions enforce structure formations in the solute-solvent system. It may also be noted that the negative value of $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ for R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ ions in solution studied in this work becomes less negative with the increase in the number of carbon atoms in the ion (n_c). According to eqn. (1) the overall volume loss represented by $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ is the sum of the contributions of the terms $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$ and \bar{V}°_{caging} . By definition $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$ (=An_c) increases with increase in n_c while \bar{V}°_{caging} (=B/n_c) decreases. Table 3 shows that \bar{V}°_{caging} is more negative than $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$ except for the ion Pr₃NH⁺, where n_c is 9. This means that for ions with lesser number of carbon atoms (n_c < 9) the volume loss due to the structure formation among the solvent molecules is comparatively less than that due to actual hiding of the hydrocarbon tails of these ions in the

hydrophobic structure (cage) formation. Such hiding is expected to be more efficient with smaller size of the solute ion (i.e., when n_c is less). Moreover, small R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ ions might cause significant electrostriction⁴, which also contributes to the volume loss. Earlier results¹ with R₄N⁺ ions in solution also show $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ for Me₄N⁺ ion (n_c=4) is more negative than that for Et₄N⁺ (n_c=8), while for Pr₄N⁺ (n_c=12) $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ is again more negative than Et₄N⁺ (n_c=8). Thus the behaviour of R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ ions, where x may be anything between 1 to 4, in solution suggests that only when n_c is sufficiently large to cause insignificant electrostriction and to make $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{H_2O}$ (=An_c) much larger than \bar{V}°_{caging} (=B/n_c), the value of $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{ion} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{cryst}$ becomes progressively more negative with increasing value of n_c.

Conclusion

Although there may be ground for some uncertainty in the estimated values of crystal radii of the R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ ions and also in the assumption of negligible electrostriction for the ions (particularly for the lower members of R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ ions) eqn. (1) seems to remain valid for the volumetric description of the hydrophobic interactions caused by these ions with non-polar hydrocarbon groups in solution. This may indicate the usefulness of eqn. (1) for predicting the value of partial molal volumes of other R_xNH_{4-x}⁺ ions (particularly the higher members) in solution when the corresponding experimental data are not available.

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